

Roundtable Discussion: The Legacy of the Biden Administration

The Biden Administration, Iran, and the Middle East

Hamad H. Albloshi

Hamad H. Albloshi is an associate professor of political science at Kuwait University. He is the author of "The Eternal Revolution: Hardliners and Conservatives in Iran." He has published several academic articles both in Arabic and English on different issues such as the relationship between Iran and Kuwait, Iran's internal politics, Kuwait's internal politics, Kuwait's political system, and the Houthis.

Mohammad Javad Zarif, Iran's former vice president for strategic affairs and former foreign minister, spoke with CNN's Fareed Zakaria in January 2025 in Davos. During the interview, Zarif said: "if today instead of president Pezeshkian you had president Jalili [Pezeshkian's competitor in the last presidential elections], you might have had a major war going on in the region [the Middle East]" (World Economic Forum, 2025). Zarif's assertion touches upon two issues: the first relates to the regional dynamic in the Middle East, especially after October 7, 2023, and the second to the internal dynamic in Iran.

Both dynamics are interrelated and might be difficult to separate from one another. Iran is a large country with a population over 80 million and an area of 1,648 million km². Iranian authorities, before and after the revolution, have been able to shape and reshape the regional structure of the Middle East. This influence intensified since the revolution because of Iran's ambitious plans to increase its involvement in the region. One way to achieve this was through the creation and support of different armed groups such as Hezbollah and Hamas, among others. Therefore, when these groups engage in wars, Iran

becomes involved, directly or indirectly in these wars. However, Iran's internal situation affects the degree of its involvement.

Iran has been ruled by an Islamic regime since 1979. Despite not being democratic, Iran has had many elections since the 1979 revolution. Competition in some of these elections has been intense. Different Islamists, including hardliners, conservatives, moderates and reformists, have participated and competed in these elections for decades.

However, by the end of President Rouhani's second term in 2021, a decision seems to have been taken to exclude reformists and moderates from major institutions, especially legislative and executive bodies. In both cases, the Guardian Council, which is responsible for approving candidates who want to run in elections, prevented them from participating in presidential and parliamentary elections. This created an atmosphere in the country where people saw elections as an ineffective tool for political change since the Guardian Council had the power to exclude certain individuals from participating. Although this is not a new practice, the Council used to approve the candidacy of strong

reformists and moderates in the past such as Hashimi Rafsanjani, Mohammad Khatami, and Hassan Rouhani. However, in recent elections, influential politicians were excluded, giving the impression that the Council “engineered” the elections in favor of the hardliners.

Therefore, many boycotted the 2020 and 2024 parliamentary elections and also boycotted the 2021 presidential elections. In 2020, only 42.5 percent of eligible Iranians voted in the parliamentary elections (Etemad, 1402 [2024]) and in 2024 only 41 percent participated (Donya-e Eqtesad, 1402 [2024]). At the same time, only 48.88 percent of eligible voters participated in the 2021 presidential elections, the lowest since the revolution, compared with 73.33 percent in 2017 (Khabaronline, 1403 [2024]).

Hardliner and conservative politicians dominated both the parliament and the presidency because their bases did not boycott the 2021 and 2024 elections. The same faction controlled the judiciary, and was therefore able to dominate all institutions in Iran. Banning reformists and moderates from running in elections was not the only reason behind the boycott. The failure to improve the economic situation in Iran may have been another reason. People overwhelmingly voted for Hassan Rouhani in 2013 and 2017 with the hope that he would bring change to their everyday lives. However, he was not able to do that, not only because of mismanagement within the country, but also because of external pressures, especially from the US under the leadership of President Donald Trump.

Rouhani and his team, including Zarif and the current foreign minister, Abbas Araqchi, were able to reach an agreement with the international community regarding Iran’s

nuclear program, known as the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) in 2015, which limited Iran’s access to nuclear materials and put its program under the observation of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). JCPOA was important because it partially opened Iran to the international community, especially to international companies which wanted to invest in the country. Iran’s economy improved after the deal. For example, when President Rouhani came to power in 2013, inflation in Iran was over 35 percent but by the end of his first term and after two years of the JCPOA, it was less than 10 percent (Central Bank of the Islamic Republic of Iran). In addition, Iran’s oil production increased after 2015 (BBC, 2019). However, these relative improvements in Iran’s economy did not last long, because President Trump decided to withdraw from the deal in 2018 and described it as “one of the worst and most one-sided transactions the United States has ever entered into” (Trump White House, 2018).

There was a chance to revive the deal again when Joe Biden came to office in 2021, before the end of Rouhani’s second term, but he did not take this step. This could have been important for improving Iran’s economy and sending a message to the Iranian people about the importance of participating in the 2021 presidential election and having a president that wants Iran to be part of the international community. The chance of a moderate being elected were low in that election since the Guardian Council excluded important moderate and reformist politicians and instead approved the candidacy of Abdolnasser Himmati, who was an unknown moderate politician. However, things might have changed on the ground if Biden had taken a step towards rejoining the deal because Himmati tried during his campaign to convince

the Iranian people that he was the right candidate for the job and criticized the hardliners' approach to foreign policy. Nevertheless, the boycott prevailed and brought Ebrahim Raisi, a hardliner, to power.

Despite this, a hardline Iranian president was willing to sit down with the Americans to negotiate the renewal of JCPOA. According to Zarif, the meeting was supposed to be held on October 9, 2023 (World Economic Forum, 2025). The meeting was canceled because of the events on October 7, 2023.

Hope emerged in Iran when the Guardian Council approved the candidacy of Masoud Pezeshkian, a reformist parliamentarian, for the 2024 presidential elections, after the death of Ebrahim Raisi in a helicopter crash. Although the move behind the Council's decision to allow a popular reformist politician to run in the election is not clear, it can be argued that reconciliation was a reason behind this decision. Additionally, the authorities in Iran rely on high participation in elections to project their legitimacy. Since participation in the 2020, 2021, and 2024 elections was low, Iranian officials may have wanted to increase participation rates. However, in the first round, participation was the lowest in the history of the Islamic Republic, at only 40 percent (Khabaronline, 1403 [2024]). But in the second round, when the election was between Pezeshkian and Jalili, participation increased to 49.8 percent (Khabaronline, 1403 [2024]). This means that the authorities at least partially achieved their goal in the second round. When Pezeshkian reached power, the Biden administration had another opportunity to revive the deal. However, it is possible that President Trump would have overturned it again on entering office.

These developments in Iran coincided with

other major events in the region. The first event occurred on October 7th, 2023, and the subsequent war in Gaza, and the second was the fall of Assad in Syria at the end of 2024. Between these two events, other developments took place as well.

Most importantly was the reaction of the Biden administration to all these events. Although Washington was not passive after October 7, it was ineffective. US Secretary of State Antony Blinken made numerous diplomatic visits to the region to end the war in Gaza, but he ultimately failed to do so. In the context of the first direct Israeli-Iranian military confrontation, such ineffectiveness could easily have led the region into a major war.

When Rasi was president, Iran retaliated for the attack on its consulate in Syria within four days, while under Pezeshkian it took longer, and it did not retaliate after the last Israeli attack in October 2024. It is true that Iran's decisions about national security are not taken solely by the president, but in collaboration with other institutions, especially the Supreme National Security Council and, most importantly, the Supreme Leader, Ali Khamenei. However, the president can influence decision-making processes regarding war and peace. Therefore, Zarif's argument in his interview with Zakaria in Davos regarding the possibility of a major war in the region could have been true, had a hardliner won the most recent presidential elections.

On the other hand, one could argue that Iranian leaders understood the cost of responding to the latest Israeli attacks. The attacks might have been very harmful to Iran and it therefore did not retaliate. Notably, Iran's leaders understand the importance of restraint. For example, a recent leaked lecture given by a brigadier general in Iran's Revolu-

tionary Guards, Behrouz 'Isbati, who fought alongside the former Syrian government, revealed that Iran neither has the desire nor the ability to engage in a major war in the region. Sabiti indicated during his lecture, when answering a question, that Iran did not want a war with the United States. Most importantly, he asserted that Iran did not have the capabilities to attack American bases in the region (Ensaf News, 1403 [2025]).

However, this does not mean that the Iranians do not want to protect themselves. In the aftermath of October 7, 2023, Iranians have discussed the possibility of changing the country's nuclear doctrine. Since Iran's nuclear program was revealed, it has insisted that the program is for the peaceful development of nuclear energy. There is even a fatwa, or a religious decree, issued by Ali Khamenei asserting that it is forbidden in Islam to build a nuclear bomb. However, since Iran's sovereignty was violated by Israel's attacks, and since its influence has weakened because of Assad's fall, some may have concluded that it is time for Iran to change its nuclear doctrine.

Different factions within the Islamic Republic might support this option to protect Iran against the possibility of future military actions or attempts to topple the current regime by a foreign adversary. Although not all politicians support this option, including Rouhani (Rouhani Hassan, 1403 [2024]), the fact that there is a discussion over this option is a significant shift in the country regarding the program. This might not have been the case, had the Biden administration been able to restrain the Israeli prime minister from directly attacking Iranian territory or escalating the situation in Gaza. Iran might have always wanted to obtain a nuclear bomb, however, the fact that Iranians are now discussing acquiring the bomb is a significant change in

the discourse within the country. Therefore, any shift in Iran's approach to its nuclear program is a result of two American presidents: Biden and Trump. The first for his hesitation in returning to the JCPOA and the other for his "maximum pressure" policy on Iran.

Negotiations with Iran are not easy and different domestic and foreign factors are often at play. It is possible to argue that given the war in Gaza, neither the Biden administration nor the Iranian government were able to successfully negotiate reviving the JCPOA, however, a stronger reaction from Biden towards the war in Gaza might have changed things on the ground. First, Israel might not have attacked Iran, and second, some Iranian officials might not have felt that having a nuclear bomb could be an option to protect their country and regime. ♦

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